

Empowering Business Analysts for Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0: Strengthening Capabilities for Digital Transformation in South Africa

Deborah Oluwadele^[0000-0002-1425-8278] and Timothy Adeliyi^[0000-0002-8034-1045]

Department of Informatics, University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa
deborah.oluwadele@up.ac.za

Abstract. Business Analysts (BAs) play a crucial role in driving innovation and facilitating data-driven decision-making, particularly in the evolving technological landscape of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0. This paper presents a practical framework for enhancing the skills of BAs to meet the demands of these new paradigms. The framework focuses on developing BAs' skills in data science, data analytics, and research and development, which are crucial for thriving in the Information economy of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Presented at the IIBA-SA 2023 Summit, the framework illustrated the use of Data Science and Analytics tools and techniques to transform customer experience. Specifically, the framework employs Sentiment Analysis to understand customer feedback and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to extract features impacting customer dissatisfaction, thereby identifying opportunities for digital transformation. Additionally, the framework introduced the Design Science Research (DSR) method, offering BAs a systematic and rigorous approach to problem-solving, innovation, and knowledge creation. Despite being a new concept for many participants, the framework generated high interest and curiosity. This paper underscores the importance of empowering BAs to adapt to the evolving technological landscape, enabling them to contribute significantly to problem-solving and knowledge creation in South Africa.

Keywords: Society 5.0, Industry 5.0, Design Science Research, IIBA, Business Analysts, Digital Transformation, IIBA Southern Africa Summit.

1 Introduction

Technological innovations are changing the way enterprises operate, fostering the emergence of new sectors, new business models, new kinds of firms, new specialist jobs [1], and presenting new competitive advantages through automation [2], robotic process automation [3], and data-driven decision making [4]. These advancements require a focus on developing a variety of specific competencies and interdisciplinary skill sets crucial for stabilizing the market and facilitating smooth transitions between different professions [5]. This is especially true in the software engineering domain. The very innovations that software developers create are reshaping their work. As IT

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professionals construct new automation tools for various industries, their work processes and tasks are substantially influenced by the technologies they develop [6].

The European Commission embraced the technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) by developing a framework to leverage these technologies in serving Society 5.0 objectives [7, 8], while the Japanese cabinet also leveraged the technologies to establish a sustainable Industry 5.0 model where production aligns with environmental boundaries and prioritize the well-being of industry workers [9, 10]. However, in the South African context, the technological innovations of the 4IR are considered a mix of blessings and curses [2]. Upon becoming the president of South Africa, President Cyril Ramaphosa's integration of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) into the national economic strategy sparked debate over its alignment with neoliberal principles like those promoted by the World Economic Forum (WEF). Concerns were expressed regarding its potential to address unemployment. This reservation is undisputable given that South Africa faces a substantial skills deficit, primarily attributed to deficiencies in its education system, which restricts the availability of managers, researchers, and workers essential for the 4IR [11]. The impacts of Industry 4.0 and Society 5.0 on work and employment are expected to be complex, possibly exacerbating inequality by decreasing the demand for low-skilled workers. Additionally, there are challenges related to inadequate infrastructure quality, indicative of governance weaknesses and state capture. The country's track record in policy development and implementation, particularly across different departments, is poor, leading to significant delays in cybersecurity and data protection [2, 11-13].

The principles of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0 can be applied in South Africa to address economic and societal challenges through innovation and digital transformation. In this context, BAs are key players in driving innovation, facilitating data-driven decision-making, and ensuring organizations remain competitive in an ever-evolving technological landscape. BAs are responsible for identifying business problems, analyzing their root causes, and ensuring they are resolved with the most feasible and valuable solutions (Weilbach et al., 2023). Although business analysis has evolved significantly, transitioning from the waterfall methodologies era to the agile approach and becoming more crucial for businesses, the specialization is laced with a plethora of challenges. One of which is that the boundaries of the domain are getting blurred as professionals in different roles increasingly integrate business analysis tasks into their daily responsibilities [14], resulting in the perception of business analysis as a diminishing practice with decreasing importance and potential for extinction. Furthermore, the BA role is often ambiguous, lacking a universally accepted definition, and is considered one of the least defined roles in IT [14-16].

The adoption of 4IR technologies in South Africa will amplify existing challenges in business analysis, given the region's economic and political landscape. Mukozho and Seymour [17] assert that the onset of the Fourth Industrial Revolution has raised significant questions about the future skills required in the business analysis profession. The study noted a lack of studies in the digital age that systematically track the evolution of necessary skills over time and stress the importance of further empirical research to inform the Business Analysis Body of Knowledge (BABOK) and to help practitioners ensure that their skills align with the demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Therefore, this study aims to present a practical framework as a guideline to enhance the competencies of BAs to meet the demands of the futuristic society and industry by leveraging the technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. This study answers the research question, “What specific competencies are required for Business Analysts (BAs) to effectively navigate and excel in futuristic society and industry, leveraging the technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution?”.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the study's background, presenting the interplay between Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0 and the role of a Business Analyst (BA) in the evolving technological landscape. Section 3 describes the research methodology; detailing the framework and the justification for its constructs, while Section 4 presents the data analysis focusing on the skills and capabilities required by a BA for Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0. The implication of the studies for the BA practice is discussed in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 provides the paper's conclusion.

2 Background

In the backdrop of Industry 5.0 and the emergence of Society 5.0, there is a growing recognition of the need for businesses to adapt to new technological advancements and societal shifts. The interplay between these concepts drives significant changes in the workforce, requiring businesses to rethink their strategies and upskill their employees to remain competitive. This paper explores the role of Business Analysts (BAs) in the evolving technological landscape, highlighting the need to acquire new capabilities to thrive in Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0. The framework presented in this paper aims to facilitate the understanding of the competencies needed to excel in the information economy, ensuring that BAs can effectively contribute to their organization's success in the digital transformation era.

2.1 Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0

The Japanese cabinet in 2016 embarked on the journey towards an intelligent, ultimately smart society under Japanese Prime Minister Shino Abe [18]. The hallmark of Society 5.0 is the vision to create a high degree of merging between cyberspace and physical space and balance economic progress with the resolution of social issues by offering products and services that specifically target various underlying needs, irrespective of location, age, gender, or language [19]. Leveraging technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), such as AI, Big data, and 5G, Society 5.0 projects a futuristic, human-centered, highly intelligent, and efficient society driven by scientific and technological innovation [20-22]. The core value of Society 5.0 is to build a human-centered, super-smart, and lean society, ensuring a comfortable and sustainable future for all [20].

Industry 4.0; a German initiative in 2011 from a high-tech strategy project [23] is hinged on the previous three industrial revolutions to enable production systems, represented by Cyber-Physical Production Systems (CPPS), autonomously make informed decisions by communicating and collaborating in real-time with "manufacturing things," leading to the flexible production of high-quality personalized products with mass efficiency [8]. The concept of Industry 5.0 evolved from its predecessor –

Industry 4.0, and started to gain traction in 2017 [9]. However, in 2021, the European Commission officially endorsed the Industry 5.0 concept following deliberations among stakeholders from research and technology organizations and funding agencies across Europe [7, 8]. Industry 5.0 acknowledges the potential of the industries to serve societal objectives beyond mere job creation and economic growth. It aims to establish a sustainable model where production aligns with environmental limits and prioritizes the well-being of industry workers. This approach supplements the current Industry 4.0 framework by emphasizing the role of research and innovation in transitioning to a European industry that is sustainable, human-centric, and resilient [7]. Atkin to Society 5.0, the core values of Industry 5.0 include human centricity by putting the needs and interests of people at the heart of production processes, sustainability, re-using, re-purposing, and recycling natural resources to reduce waste and environmental impact and resilience, developing a higher degree of robustness in industrial production for agile response to geo-political shifts and natural emergencies [20].

2.2 The Interplay between Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0

The interplay between the futuristic society and industry is such that the industrial revolution will drive societal development, while societal transformation will propel the next industrial revolution [18, 20]. This is because both concepts share similar opportunities and challenges. As analyzed by Huang et al. (2022), the integration of cyberspace and physical space, known as Human-Cyber-Physical Systems (HCPS), is a critical technology for both Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0. This involves human involvement in decision-making processes and interaction loops. Additionally, the development of the Human Digital Twin (HDT) is crucial for modeling and simulating human behavior in these systems. Another common area is Greentelligent Manufacturing (GIM), which focuses on using AI for sustainable and green manufacturing practices. Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) is also a key research area, aiming to merge human and machine intelligence to enhance innovation in manufacturing. The transformation brought by Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0 will impact future jobs and workers. While automation may lead to job losses in some areas, new roles like data analysts and automated guided vehicle coordinators will emerge [5, 6, 20]. Hence, stakeholders need to adapt to these changes efficiently to create smart, resilient manufacturing systems that predict, respond to, and recover from disruptions.

2.3 The Evolving Role of a BA in Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0

In the era of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0, characterized by rapid technological advancements and the integration of digital technologies into every aspect of society, the role of Business Analysts (BAs) has become increasingly vital. Business Analysis allows organizations to express their needs and reasons for change and design and define solutions that can provide value to the organization. A business analyst (BA) is responsible for identifying business problems, analyzing their root causes, and ensuring that problems are resolved with the most efficient solutions that deliver value to all stakeholders [1]. BAs are key players in driving innovation, facilitating data-driven decision-making, and ensuring that organizations remain competitive. The International Institute of Business Analysis (IIBA) defines business analysis as the process of facilitating

change within an organization by identifying needs and proposing solutions that provide value to stakeholders [24]. The evolving landscape of industry and society leads to increased automation of physical and repetitive tasks, enhancing the utilization of solutions integrating digital technologies to gain data-driven insight into the customers' pain points [2, 3, 25]. However, this shift also creates opportunities for new jobs that require different skills and competencies [20].

The Industrial Development Think Tank has expressed concerns about South Africa's ability to adapt to this revolution [26]. Cross-national comparisons and national studies often indicate that the country's technological capability and level of digitalization are inadequate [27, 28]. The fear of increased joblessness and inequality looms with the advent of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR). The McKinsey Global Institute has projected substantial workforce disruption by 2030, with automation potentially displacing up to 13% of current work activities in South Africa. The impact of the 4IR on jobs is a pressing concern, highlighting the need for proactive measures to address potential job displacement and mitigate inequality in the face of advancing technologies [29]. A study conducted to explore public opinion on the impact of technologies of the 4IR on South Africa reported that technology aversion is high among South Africans as workers who are vulnerable to being displaced by automation and artificial intelligence will be more hostile to technological change in society [2]. Technology aversion presents as a barrier to technology adoption to solve the economic and societal challenges in South Africa. This threat is even more pronounced for BAs, given the context of the problems experienced already in the domain.

Despite this context, the role of BAs is not about to go extinct any time soon, given the fact that organizations need them to enhance their understanding of the utilization of solutions integrating digital technologies, their value delivery, and a deeper insight into customers' viewpoints. However, to meet the demands of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0 and the ability to solve real-world problems, BAs must possess unique competencies beyond traditional business analysis. Society 5.0 represents a human-centered society that leverages technological advancements, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and big data, to address societal challenges and improve the quality of life. Industry 5.0, on the other hand, focuses on the integration of cyber-physical systems into manufacturing processes to create smart factories and drive efficiency. In this context, the Fourth Industrial Revolution has put the future skills of the profession into question [17]. The role of BAs has expanded to include an understanding of data analytics, machine learning, and other advanced technologies to drive the identification of the use cases of the 4IR technologies in improving business processes. As inferred from Kusiak [30], in the context of smart manufacturing, BAs must possess the skills to analyze large datasets, identify patterns and trends, and make data-driven recommendations to drive business growth and innovation. The literature emphasizes the importance of collaboration and interdisciplinary skills for BAs in Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0. As organizations become more interconnected and reliant on technology, BAs must be able to collaborate effectively with data scientists, engineers, and other stakeholders to translate business requirements into technical solutions [17].

This paper presents a practical framework as a guideline to enhance the competencies of BAs to meet the demands of the futuristic society and industry by leveraging the

technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The framework focuses on equipping BAs with the tools and techniques necessary to excel in a data-driven environment. The implementation of this framework marks a significant step forward in preparing BAs in Southern Africa for the challenges and opportunities presented by Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0. Organizations can remain agile, innovative, and competitive in the global marketplace by empowering BAs with the skills they need to thrive in this new era.

3 Method

3.1 The BA 4IR Competency Framework

The BA 4IR Competency framework is designed to guide BAs in acquiring the competencies necessary to thrive in leveraging technologies of the 4IR in the era of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0. This framework was introduced at the 2023 BA Summit Southern Africa as a practical approach to addressing the evolving role of BAs in a rapidly changing technological landscape. Hinging on the comparison between the goal, value, organization and technology dimensions of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0 drawn by Huang, Wang [20] depicted in Fig. 1 and the work of Ellitan [31] on competing in the era of industrial revolution 4.0 and Society 5.0., we map out the competencies required by business analysts to continue facilitating change within an organization by identifying needs and proposing solutions that provide value to stakeholders in the context of the evolving technological landscape for the futuristic society and industry. From the different dimensions identified by Huang et al., we select themes relevant to the competencies of a BA and map out the requirements and the skills needed to provide value for each theme.

Fig. 1. Comparison Framework for Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0 [20]

3.2 Key Dimensions of the BA 4IR Competency Framework

1. **Human Literacy:** From the goal dimension of Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0 (Figure 1), BAs need to be human-centric. They should place humans at the center of design, decision-making, and problem-solving processes to create more intuitive, effective, and meaningful products, services, and systems for people. This competency includes empathy coupled with excellent communication skills to convey ideas effectively. Collaboration skills are also essential for working with diverse stakeholders, adaptability is critical in rapidly changing environments, and ethical awareness is necessary to make responsible decisions. Notably, data literacy is vital for acquiring human literacy to analyze and interpret data to drive meaningful insights. Possessing these skills will enable BAs to contribute to a human-centered approach, which is a central goal of Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0, ensuring that the needs of individuals are prioritized in technological and societal advancements. Adopting the principle of democratization of technology is expedient in achieving human literacy.
2. **Research Literacy:** Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0 places research and development at the forefront of manufacturing. Therefore, BAs need to acquire competencies in research and development. It is important to note that research in Information Technology (IT) differs from other disciplines, such as Social Sciences. It is a discipline that requires practical solutions to complex problems and a problem-oriented research methodology. The Design Science Research (DSR) is one such methodology. This methodology, popular in various disciplines, including information systems, computer science, engineering, and business, focuses on creating and evaluating artifacts like models, methods, and tools to solve complex problems and improve processes. Using the DSR methodology as a guide for Research in IT, BAs must possess capabilities to identify problems, analyze data, propose innovative solutions, and evaluate their effectiveness. Proficiency in relevant tools and techniques for data analysis, modeling, and visualization is crucial, as is effective communication to convey complex ideas and solutions or tell data stories to stakeholders. Additionally, collaboration skills are essential for working with cross-functional teams to develop and implement solutions. Being adaptable to changing technologies and methodologies and having a strong ethical awareness are key competencies needed to succeed in this role in the futuristic industry and society. By applying design science research methods, a business analyst can document best practices in business analysis, contribute to knowledge creation, and provide valuable insights for future generations of business analysts.
3. **Process and Product Literacy:** The organization dimension of Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0 (figure 1) requires the BAs to add value in industrial contexts of manufacturing cells, production factories, and supply chains and as a service person in the societal context. In this context, BAs must possess process literacy

- an understanding of industrial processes and supply chain operations, and product literacy - the knowledge of products and services within the industry. To acquire these competencies, however, BAs need technological literacy to gain familiarity with emerging technologies like AI and IoT, analytical skills for data analysis and process improvement, problem-solving skills to address challenges and propose solutions, communication skills for effective stakeholder engagement; adaptability to respond to industry and societal changes; collaboration skills, for working in diverse teams; ethical awareness, to understand and align with societal values; and a commitment to continuous learning, to stay updated with industry trends. These skills are essential for Business Analysts to navigate the complexities of Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0, contributing to organizational success and societal advancement.

4. Technology and Data Literacy: The technology dimension enables the goal, value, and organization dimensions of Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0 (Figure 1). The core values of Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0 are to put the needs and interests of people at the heart of production processes and ensure sustainability by reusing, re-purposing, and recycling natural resources to reduce waste and environmental impact. Also, resilience for developing a higher degree of robustness in industrial production for agile response to geo-political shifts and natural emergencies and to leverage technologies of the 4IR, such as AI, Big data, and 5G, for a futuristic, human-centered, highly intelligent, and efficient society driven by scientific and technological innovation ensuring a comfortable and sustainable future for all require BAs to acquire competency in technology and data. BAs should understand emerging technologies such as AI, big data, digital twins, and IoT, and how these technologies can be applied to solve problems in the industry and society. BAs should also be proficient in analyzing large datasets, have a good understanding of technical concepts related to software development, systems integration, and data management, and be adept at identifying problems and proposing solutions. Effective communication skills are crucial for explaining complex technical concepts to non-technical stakeholders and collaborating with cross-functional teams. Additionally, BAs should be adaptable and willing to continuously update their skills and be aware of ethical issues related to data privacy, security, and bias in AI algorithms. Developing these skills can help them contribute to the digital transformation of industries and societies in the futuristic industry and society.

While the IIBA Business Analysis Competency Model outlines the domain, technical, business, and soft skills required to fulfill the BA role [32], The 4IR demands new and faster ways of work, including a more technical-focused BA, as the technological complexity increases [17]. Based on the BA competency requirements for the goals, values, organization, and technology dimensions of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0, Fig. 2 presents a network diagram emphasizing the flows within the BA 4IR

Competency framework. It helps locate dominant contributions to an overall flow between the competencies required per dimension.

Fig. 2. Network Diagram of Dimension to Competency Flow of the BA 4IR Competency Framework.

4 Competency Mapping to the BABOK Knowledge Areas

The Business Analysis Core Concept Model™ (BACCM™) is a foundational framework within business analysis, offering a universal understanding of the discipline's fundamental principles. This model encapsulates the essence of business analysis, providing clarity and coherence to practitioners irrespective of their background, industry, methodology, or organizational hierarchy. Comprising six key terms, the BACCM facilitates meaningful discussions among business analysts and fosters a shared understanding of business analysis concepts and their interrelationships [32].

The BACCM identifies six core concepts: Change, Need, Solution, Stakeholder, Value, and Context. These concepts are regarded as fundamental ideas essential to business analysis. Each concept holds equal importance, forming a comprehensive framework for conducting business analysis activities. While the BACCM provides a conceptual framework for understanding business analysis principles, the BA Knowledge Areas provide a practical framework for applying those principles in real-world business analysis projects. Together, they offer a comprehensive and integrated approach to business analysis, combining conceptual understanding with practical application.

The Knowledge areas represent areas of specific business analysis expertise that encompass several tasks, including business analysis planning and monitoring, elicitation and collaboration, requirements life cycle management, strategy analysis, requirements analysis and design definition, and solution analysis. These knowledge areas are mapped to the competencies identified in the BA 4IR Competency Framework depicted in Table 1.

The Business Analysis Planning and Monitoring (BAPM) knowledge area (KA) requires competencies to enhance the effectiveness of planning and monitoring activities. For example, adaptability, collaboration, and empathy ensure that stakeholder engagement is productive and inclusive. Problem-solving, data analysis, and research competencies are necessary in assessing risks and selecting appropriate techniques and tools for BA activities. Continuous learning and emerging technology literacy help keep business analysis practices current. Ethical awareness ensures that all these activities are conducted transparently. Process and product literacy provide context for informed decisions during planning and monitoring.

In the Elicitation and Collaboration KA, competencies like problem-solving, adaptability, collaboration, technical proficiency, and research support Bas' preparation for elicitation. Data analysis, process literacy, and emerging technology literacy help explore and identify relevant information. Ethical awareness, empathy, technical proficiency, and data analysis ensure the accuracy and consistency of the information elicited. Product literacy, continuous learning, and technical proficiency promote a shared understanding of BA information, while collaboration, empathy, and ethical awareness ensure stakeholder participation in business analysis activities.

Table 1. 4IR BA Competency to BABOK Knowledge Area Mapping

Competencies	BAPM KA	Elicitation and Collaboration KA	Requirements Life Cycle Management KA	Strategy Analysis KA	Requirements Analysis and Design Definition KA	Solution Evaluation KA
Problem-Solving	X	X	X	X	X	X
Adaptability	X	X	X	X	X	X
Data Analysis	X	X	X	X	X	X
Ethical Awareness	X	X	X	X	X	X
Collaboration	X	X	X	X	X	X
Technical Proficiency		X	X	X	X	X
Continuous Learning	X	X	X	X	X	X
Empathy	X	X	X	X	X	X
Research	X	X	X	X	X	X

Process Literacy	X	X	X	X	X	X
Product Literacy	X	X	X	X	X	X
Emerging Technology Literacy	X	X	X	X	X	X

Requirements Life Cycle Management focuses on managing requirements from inception to retirement. competencies like problem-solving, technical proficiency, research, and product literacy are crucial for tracing requirements. Data analysis, technical proficiency, emerging technology literacy, product literacy, and continuous learning ensure accuracy and consistency during the entire requirements life cycle. Collaboration, empathy, problem-solving, and product literacy help rank requirements in the order of relative importance. Adaptability, problem-solving, ethical awareness, and technical proficiency evaluate proposed changes, while collaboration, empathy, ethical awareness, and process literacy ensure clear communication.

The Strategy Analysis KA involves understanding business contexts, defining change strategy, and aligning proposed solutions with business goals. Data analysis, research, technical proficiency, process literacy, and empathy enable an understanding of the need for change and its impacts. Collaboration, problem-solving, ethical awareness, and continuous learning help guide the development of the change strategy. Data analysis, technical proficiency, emerging technology literacy, and ethical awareness are essential for understanding the consequences of internal and external forces on an enterprise. Problem-solving, adaptability, collaboration, product literacy, process literacy, and continuous learning help develop and assess alternative approaches to change.

Requirements Analysis and Design Definition KA organizes, specifies, models requirements, and identifies potential design options. Technical proficiency, research, process proficiency, and data analysis competencies are required to analyze, synthesize, and refine elicitation results into requirements and designs. Problem-solving, collaboration, and technical proficiency ensure that requirements meet quality standards. Empathy, collaboration, ethical awareness, and adaptability align requirements with business needs. Product proficiency, process proficiency, technical proficiency, and emerging technology literacy ensure that requirements achieve pre-stated objectives. Research, continuous learning, problem-solving, adaptability, and data analysis identify improvement opportunities and design options. Collaboration, empathy, ethical awareness, and emerging technology literacy estimate value and select an appropriate design alternative.

Solution Evaluation KA assesses the performance of a solution in use to ensure it meets the business requirements and delivers the expected business value. Data analysis, technical proficiency, and research competencies help BAs define performance measures and evaluate the effectiveness of a solution. Problem-solving, data analysis, and process literacy provide insights into performance concerning value. Empathy, technical proficiency, and ethical awareness determine internal factors restricting value realization. Collaboration, product, and emerging technology literacy are needed to determine external factors restricting value realization. Problem-solving, collaboration,

adaptability, and continuous learning help understand the differences between potential and actual value and recommend actions.

5 Framework Implementation

The Business Analysis Summit Southern Africa - the annual flagship event for BAs in Southern Africa gathers a delegate of over 300 Business Analysts and their employers to discuss how their role can provide business value and support strategic change. The call for paper for the summit themed “Elevate. Empower. Excel: Inspiring the Future of Business Analysis” opined that achieving growth necessitates venturing beyond one's comfort zone. It involves continually seeking new knowledge, understanding, and moments of insight with a mindset of the willingness to teach others and to learn from them, along with a constant desire to progress. This attitude is stated to fuel personal development and enable individuals to maintain their focus and excel in their field. The 2023 event was a three-day event consisting of four tracks. Track one was themed on the sustainability mindset, while tracks two, three, and four were themed on leadership and collaboration, business analysis mastery, and maturing your practice, respectively.

As academics, both authors have been actively involved in the IIBA-SA community since 2018, while the first author has a background in BA consultancy. They both play key roles in developing learning and development strategies for BAs in the KwaZulu-Natal region of South Africa. Their efforts include conducting university workshops to educate students on best practices in business analysis and organizing and facilitating fortnightly Tools and Techniques sessions for BAs in all provinces in South Africa. These sessions provide practicing BAs in South Africa with an hour of training from global speakers, enhancing their knowledge of tools and techniques in the field. The authors' experience bridging academia and industry has inspired them to present at the conference's third track.

The 50-minute presentation to the BA Summit delegates was titled “Master of Business Analysis (MBA) – Growing your Imprint for the NextGen Business Analysts”. The presentation hinged on the fact that the role of a business analyst becomes increasingly vital as the world transitions into Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0. Industry 5.0 emphasizes human-cobot collaboration, and Society 5.0 envisions a seamless fusion of cyberspace and physical space, both driving innovation across all sectors. This evolution underscores the need for intensified partnerships between academia and business analysts to co-create value through evidence-based practices and collaborative problem-solving. They emphasize the need for enhanced data science and data analytic skills as key to evolved business analysis practice and modeled data-driven problem-solving using Sentiment Analysis to identify customer pain points via negative sentiments, Principal Component analysis to reduce the dimensionality of the features extracted from the negative sentiments and identifying problems worth solving, and finally the use of Design Science Research for research and development in IT and knowledge creation by publishing business analysis artifacts, creating evidence of best

practices in business analysis for the next generation of BAS and ensuring the sustainability of the practice.

Both speakers delivered their presentations simultaneously, employing a case study approach to enhance delegates' ability to relate the discussed problems and solutions to their work contexts. The presentation sparked significant interest and curiosity among delegates regarding the concepts of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0, which is evident from the substantial number of questions received at the session's conclusion. Additionally, ten delegates patiently waited in a queue to engage with the authors and seek further insights. The IIBA SA leadership also met with the authors and expressed alignment with the sentiments shared by previous scholars [2, 11-13] on the blurring of professional lines, the diminishing importance of the practice, and the increasing importance of digital transformation programs for BAs. The community leadership adopted Data Analytics as the overarching theme for the first quarter of 2024 and re-invited the authors to present the same topic for the first tools and techniques session in 2024.

The framework will be further evangelized through training programs, workshops, and mentoring sessions for BAs and BA managers. By presenting a practical approach to address the evolving role of BAs in a rapidly changing technological landscape BAs with the necessary skills and competencies, the framework aims to enhance their professional development and ensure they remain relevant in the digital age.

6 Conclusion

The presented framework offers a practical approach to enhance the skills of Business Analysts (BAs) in Southern Africa, aligning them with the demands of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0. BAs play a crucial role in driving innovation and facilitating data-driven decision-making in a rapidly evolving technological landscape. The framework, introduced at the IIBA-SA 2023 Summit, emphasizes the importance of continuous learning among BAs to adapt to the changing environment effectively.

By modeling collaborative problem-solving using factorial analysis, sentiment analysis, and the design science research (DSR) method, the framework provides BAs with the tools to solve real-world business problems and publish their solutions in academic journals. Despite being new concepts for many participants, the framework was positively received, highlighting the need for BAs to evolve their skills to meet future challenges. While the IIBA Core Competencies Model describes the competencies required from BAs to perform in their roles, these competencies are not specifically mapped to the contexts of the 4IR or the potentials of technologies from the era to ensure the agility of industries and sustainability of societies and enhance the lives of individuals. Therefore, this study mapped the six BA Knowledge Areas to the competencies required for a BA to thrive in the context of the 4IR to create value in the futuristic industry and society.

The framework is key to empowering BAs in Southern Africa to contribute effectively to organizational success and produce documented evidence of best practices in the domain. By mapping the necessary competencies BAs require to provide value in

the futuristic society and industry, the framework aims to ensure that BAs remain relevant and valuable in the era of Society 5.0 and Industry 5.0, ultimately driving innovation and facilitating sustainable growth in their region.

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